

The Impact of Electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM) on Consumers' Purchase Intention for Electronic Products in Tehran

(Derived from a Master's Thesis in Executive Management, Islamic Azad University)¹

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ABSTRACT

In a world where individuals are surrounded by virtual environments and digital content, the various impacts of this space on people's lives and decisions are undeniable. Simultaneously, advertising in this realm plays an essential and evident role by introducing products or services to consumers and persuading them toward purchase decisions. However, in recent years, low-quality advertising has led to consumer distrust in Iran. Amidst this, conversations and discussions occurring within social networks seem to play a significant role. Given this context, the present study aims to investigate the impact of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) on consumers' purchase intention for electronic products, along with several influencing factors. This research is applied and descriptive in nature, and the data collection tool was a questionnaire. The statistical population comprised all customers of Tehran's Grand Bazaar who were exposed to eWOM prior to making a purchase. A convenience sampling method was employed, resulting in the analysis of 363 completed questionnaires. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to assess the data. The average extracted variance (AVE) values were above 0.50, indicating acceptable convergent validity of the model. The results revealed that the variables of consumer expertise, source expertise, and frequency of eWOM had standardized regression coefficients of -0.208, 0.393, and 0.175 respectively, in relation to perceived credibility. Furthermore, perceived credibility demonstrated a significant correlation with purchase intention with a coefficient of 0.564, as all t-values exceeded 1.96. The findings also showed that an increase in consumer expertise leads to reduced trust in eWOM, and vice versa. Moreover, the perceived credibility of eWOM serves as a mediating variable in the relationship between the study variables and purchase intention.

Keywords:

Word-of-mouth advertising, electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), consumer purchase intention, perceived credibility

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving world of electronic commerce, businesses are increasingly compelled to establish more effective communication with their

customers (Asgharzadeh, 2019). Electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) has emerged as one of the most influential marketing tools in this environment, expanding across platforms such as social media, blogs, product review websites, and online discussion forums. It plays a pivotal role in shaping consumer

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decision-making processes (Cheung & Lee, 2012). The internet not only serves as the primary medium for interaction but also acts as a powerful marketing tool through which companies can enhance brand awareness (Sharifpour, 2017). This form of advertising, originally conceptualized by Katz and Lazarsfeld (1966), essentially involves the informal transmission of consumer experiences and opinions about products or services. Unlike conventional advertising, it operates beyond the control of companies and significantly influences others' purchasing behavior (Khamoushi Sarabi, 2021). With the continued expansion of internet access and the growing importance of trust in digital environments, electronic word-of-mouth has evolved into a widespread medium for sharing experiences and recommendations (Golshan, 2020). This study focuses on the critical role of eWOM in fostering trust and aims to examine the relationships among message sender expertise, message receiver expertise, and message frequency with perceived credibility—and ultimately, the impact of this perceived credibility on consumers' purchase intentions. The ultimate goal is to identify and explain the key factors influencing purchase decisions through the proposed conceptual model.

Unlike formal advertising, electronic word-of-mouth is based on real consumer experiences and can affect others' purchasing decisions without the direct intervention of companies (Khamoushi Sarabi, 2021). The growing use of the internet and the rise of social media have made it common for individuals to review others' experiences before making a purchase. Consumers often base their decisions on the author's expertise, the credibility of the message, and the frequency of exposure to such messages (Sharifpour, 2017). This process not only reduces the perceived risk associated with purchasing but also increases trust in online transactions.

In such a context, trust in eWOM is recognized as a key factor in consumer behavior. Satisfied customers share their experiences with others, potentially initiating a chain of referrals and recommendations

that can ultimately increase brand sales (Golshan, 2020). Accordingly, this study investigates the relationships among sender and receiver expertise, message quantity, perceived credibility, and their role in strengthening purchase intention.

As for the research objectives, the present study seeks to examine the effect of electronic word-of-mouth on the purchase intention of customers (consumers), which can be summarized as follows:

- To assess the effectiveness of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) on the behavior of consumers purchasing electronic products.
- To identify the key factors influencing consumer purchase decisions for electronic products within the context of eWOM.
- The practical objective of this study is to examine the impact of electronic word-of-mouth on consumers' purchase intention for electronic products. Therefore, the research seeks to understand consumer behavior, identify the factors that enhance purchase intention, and gather insights in this regard. The findings can benefit all public and private entities—both governmental and non-governmental—that utilize the internet to promote, market, and sell their products and services.

Figure (1-1): The Conceptual Model of the Study

In accordance with the research objectives, the researcher has defined the boundaries of the study as follows:

The time scope of this research covers a six-month period, from July 2022 to December 2022. The geographical scope includes all customers and buyers (internet users) who search for their desired products online, are influenced by electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), and ultimately intend to make their purchase in Tehran's Grand Bazaar. This

group constitutes the population analyzed in this study.

2. Literature Review – Domestic Studies

Various domestic studies have examined the impact of word-of-mouth advertising (both traditional and electronic) on the behavior of Iranian consumers. Key findings from selected research are summarized as follows:

- **Parsanejad et al. (2019)** found that word-of-mouth advertising significantly influences the installation and retention of mobile games, playing an important role in profitability.
- **Jalilian et al. (2012)** concluded that electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), by enhancing brand equity—excluding brand awareness—positively affects purchase intention for DELL laptops.
- **Ghatari et al. (2019)** emphasized that eWOM increases cognitive engagement among sports consumers and thereby influences their purchase intentions.
- **Mohammadian et al. (2019)** analyzed that eWOM enhances tourists' trust in Iran as a destination and plays a vital role in shaping European tourists' travel decisions.
- **Davari et al. (2015)** identified various dimensions of word-of-mouth (intensity, positive and negative potential, content, and corporate image) as influential in consumers' willingness to use insurance services.
- **Ahmadi Esfahani (2021)** demonstrated that eWOM has a direct role in the adoption of mobile banking services.
- **Farrokhi et al. (2017)** confirmed a positive relationship between word-of-mouth and brand preference, brand association, and brand awareness in the flour industry.
- **Zohreh Dehdashti et al. (2015)** found that ease of use, satisfaction, and repurchase intention enhance word-of-mouth, although trust was not found to be significantly influential.
- **Esmailpour et al. (Issue No. 33)**, in a study on Instagram, concluded that communicative factors such as similarity and normative influence significantly

impact eWOM, which in turn affects impulse buying, purchase intention, and brand engagement. However, trust did not show a significant effect.

This body of research confirms the growing significance of eWOM in shaping trust, brand value, cognitive involvement, and purchase intention across various domains such as mobile gaming, tourism, financial services, sports, and online retail.

3. Literature Review – International Studies

Numerous international studies have explored the influence of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) on purchase decision-making, brand image, and consumer behavior under various conditions. Key findings include:

- Nilashi (2022): During the COVID-19 pandemic, electronic trust was found to reduce perceived risk and increase travel intention.
- Indrawati (2021): Information obtained via TikTok had a positive effect on purchase intention.
- Imanina (2016): Both eWOM and electronic service quality simultaneously influenced the purchase intention of Xiaomi brand users on Facebook.
- Sharma (2017): eWOM had a stronger effect on brand image than on direct purchase intention; however, brand image itself significantly influenced purchase intention.
- Sharifpour (2017): eWOM had a positive and significant impact on Samsung brand purchase intention through brand association.
- Ismagilova (2019): eWOM directly and positively influenced purchase intention.
- Zhang (2010); Park & Lee (2008): Online reviews significantly affected purchase decisions, consumer behavior, and product success in the market.
- Qureshi (2020): In the Irish apparel industry, eWOM influenced purchasing

decisions, with source credibility playing a vital role in building trust.

- **Nofal (2022)**: eWOM sources and social ties on social media significantly affected consumers' purchase intentions.
- **Chowdhury (2016)**: In the telecommunications sector of Bangladesh, eWOM had a positive effect on purchase intention.
- **Gultom (2022)**: Among Netflix users, both eWOM and brand image had simultaneous effects on purchasing decisions.

4. Theoretical Framework

4.1 Electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM)

With the expansion of modern technologies such as the internet, mobile phones, and social media, the landscape of marketing communication has undergone a significant transformation, and electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) has emerged as a key tool in influencing consumer purchasing behavior (Imanina, 2016). Today's consumers can share their content instantly—upon entering a store or unboxing a product. Various formats, including videos, likes, ratings, and textual comments, enable greater interaction. Moreover, 63% of individuals report that they pay special attention to other users' reviews before purchasing an unfamiliar product (Qureshi, 2020). In such a digital environment, eWOM has become a crucial source of influence on consumers' attitudes and buying behaviors—particularly when the product is unfamiliar or its quality is difficult to evaluate (Herr, 1991). eWOM content can take different forms, including brief product reviews, participation in online discussions, or reposting/sharing existing content (Gong, 2017). The motivations behind generating such content may include altruism, concern for others, financial incentives, or personal satisfaction. Since eWOM stems from the direct experiences of fellow consumers, it is often perceived as more trustworthy than traditional marketing advertisements (Smith & Park, 1992). Consequently, electronic word-of-mouth is considered a significant factor in shaping purchase intention, as it helps reduce perceived risk and increases the likelihood of consumer purchase.

- **Leong (2022)**: The quality, credibility, relevance, and attitude toward eWOM information influenced its perceived usefulness, thereby affecting purchase acceptance and intention.

In summary, eWOM—especially within social media platforms—is a critical factor in building trust, reducing perceived risk, and increasing purchase intention among global consumers.

4.2 Purchase Intention

Purchase intention refers to a customer's mental willingness and deliberate intention to buy a specific product or service, and it arises from the individual's perception of the brand's or seller's performance (Sadrudin, 2021). It is considered a critical part of the purchasing decision-making process in which the customer is actively seeking to make a purchase (Shokoohi Fallah, 2018). With the growth of the internet, electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) has become a powerful factor in either strengthening or weakening purchase intention. This form of communication can influence buying decisions through the positive or negative experiences shared by other consumers (Sharifpour, 2017). Several factors may enhance or diminish purchase intention, such as personality traits, access to information, others' opinions, and endorsements by celebrities (Azami & Hosseini, 2016; Allahverdi et al., 2021). It is important to note that purchase intention is not equivalent to the act of purchase itself; rather, it serves as a predictive indicator of it (Norouzi, 2018). Additionally, this intention is influenced by individual attitudes, perceived social norms, and behavioral control (Aryan, 2018). Ultimately, an accurate understanding of purchase intention helps marketers design more effective online advertising strategies (Qureshi, 2020).

4.3 Purchase Decision-Making

The development of the internet and social media has given rise to electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), which plays a significant

role in influencing consumer behavior and decision-making (Madadi, 2019). Consumers tend to rely more heavily on others' opinions, particularly in high-risk purchasing situations (Jeong & Jang, 2011; Jalilian, 2012). The purchase decision-making process is a multi-stage journey that includes need recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decision, and post-purchase behavior (Heydari, 2018; Zarei, 2019). Today, social media platforms have become an integral part of daily life, providing a space for consumers to exchange experiences. These platforms influence brand awareness, attitudes, and purchase intentions (Qureshi, 2020). Consumers obtain necessary information either from prior experiences (internal search) or through others' experiences (external search) (Serajpour, 2021). Buying behavior is influenced by both internal factors (such as personal characteristics) and external factors (such as product design, advertising, pricing, and platform features) (Beatty & Ferrell, 1998). Within this process, the "consumer's black box" plays a critical role, encompassing personal attributes and internal psychological processes (Yousefi Khorrani, 2021; Azimi, 2018). The greater the gap between a customer's expectations and the actual performance of the product, the higher the level of dissatisfaction (Mohtashamzadeh, 2017).

4.4 Perceived Credibility of Electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM)

The perceived credibility of electronic word-of-mouth plays a pivotal role in determining how influential the information will be on consumer behavior. The more credible the information is perceived to be, the more likely it is to be used in purchase decision-making. This factor is particularly critical in online environments, where individuals often exchange information without prior acquaintance (Ismagilova, 2019). Credibility is considered the first step in the persuasion process, in which information may be regarded as convincing. The perception of persuasiveness can be observed in the trustworthiness of the information (Erkan &

Evans, 2018). Filieri (2015) states that the credibility or accuracy of information affects its ability to persuade consumers, as trust in the information is derived from such evaluations. According to Nan (2009), credibility is often reinforced by supporting evidence. Wetzels (2014) emphasizes that credibility is closely related to believability, which includes characteristics such as reliability, persuasiveness, and plausibility. It has been demonstrated that credible information positively impacts its perceived usefulness. eWOM perceived as credible by consumers is more likely to be accepted and facilitates information adoption (Filieri, 2015). Information that is perceived as accurate, trustworthy, credible, and persuasive contributes to increased credibility (Ho, 2021). Therefore, perceived credibility in eWOM refers to the level of confidence and value that the message recipient attributes to the source or communication channel (Self, 1996; Naqizadeh, 2016). This credibility is often defined through concepts such as believability, trustworthiness, honesty, and impartiality. In his cognitive authority theory, Wilson (1983) highlights that credible sources—whether individuals, organizations, or tools—affect others' attitudes and decisions due to their competence and trustworthiness (Afshani, 2014).

4.5 Message Credibility

Message credibility refers to the extent to which the information contained in a message is perceived as trustworthy and believable by the audience (Ismagilova, 2019). This concept reflects the consumer's perception of honesty, accuracy, and consistency between claims and actual performance (McKenzie & Lutz, 1989; Naqizadeh, 2016). Herbig and Milewicz (1995) similarly defined credibility as the alignment between speech and action.

Various studies have examined credibility from the perspectives of the source, medium, and message. Notably, Obermiller and Spangenberg (1998) introduced the concept of advertising skepticism, referring to doubt

regarding the truthfulness of advertising claims. According to the Cognitive Response Theory, credible sources are more effective when the audience holds a negative attitude toward the message, whereas even low-credibility sources can be persuasive for positively inclined audiences (Afshani, 2014). The quality and structure of the message play critical roles in persuasion. Consumers tend to trust a message when its information is comprehensible, relevant, and aligned with their needs. A highly credible message enhances the consumer's willingness to trust electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM). According to Attribution Theory, message credibility increases when the audience perceives the sender's motive as sharing genuine product features rather than merely attempting to sell (McKenzie & Lutz, 1989). Characteristics such as message clarity, number of arguments, expressive appeal, repetition, and delivery method all influence perceived credibility (Slater & Rouner, 1996). Overall, three main factors contribute to message credibility:

1. **Message structure** – how the components are organized;
2. **Message content** – the quality and strength of the information;
3. **Message delivery** – the manner in which the message is presented by the source (Afshani, 2014).

4.6 Source Credibility

In the context of social media, audiences often seek to verify the identity and credibility of the message source, as citing a credible source can significantly enhance trust and increase message acceptance. In other words, source credibility refers to the degree of trust that the message receiver places in the sender. This credibility primarily depends on two key factors: expertise and trustworthiness (Khoshroudi, 2015). Newell and Goldsmith (2001) define corporate credibility as the company's ability to fulfill its claims and maintain honesty in its advertising. Similarly, Keller (1998) argues that corporate credibility reflects the consumer's belief in the company's capability to design and deliver products or

services that meet customer needs (Afshani, 2014). Thus, the more expert and trustworthy the source is perceived to be, the more likely it is that the message will be accepted by the audience.

4.7 Source Expertise

Source expertise refers to the audience's perception of the message sender as a knowledgeable, experienced, and skilled individual capable of delivering accurate and reliable information (Khoshroudi, 2015). This expertise increases the likelihood of message acceptance, reduces skepticism, and enhances the persuasive power of the message. Factors such as age, managerial experience, and social background can also serve as indicators of perceived expertise (Ohanian, 1990). In the context of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), source expertise plays a critical role in reducing uncertainty and building consumer trust. Expertise can be inferred from cues such as the length of time the user has been active on a platform or the number of reviews they have submitted. Research has shown that source expertise significantly affects purchase intention. For instance, a study by Zainal et al. (2017) demonstrated that source expertise in eWOM had a meaningful impact on consumers' intention to book hotels.

Therefore, the more expert the source is perceived to be, the more persuasive and influential the message becomes (Ismagilova, 2019).

4.8 Consumer Expertise

Consumer expertise refers to individuals who possess specific knowledge, skills, or experience in a particular domain and are capable of providing accurate information (Qureshi, 2020). Those who are more educated or informed in a given area are recognized as expert consumers. They tend to have higher confidence in their purchase decisions and are less reliant on external opinions. Such expertise enhances their ability to process information efficiently and reduces the perceived risk when purchasing unfamiliar products (Ehsani, B.,

2014). Consumers with higher levels of expertise, due to their greater knowledge and experience, are better able to analyze information quickly and accurately. As a result, they are often viewed as reliable sources by other consumers (Gilly et al., 1998). eWOM messages disseminated by such experts are generally more influential and have become a primary source for online consumers in evaluating product quality.

While experience and expertise are closely related, there is a key distinction between the two. Experience stems from actual usage of a product, whereas expertise refers to the audience's perception of the sender's knowledge and competence in a specific subject area (Ehsani, 2015). Expertise not only increases the accuracy of purchase decisions but also plays a crucial role in validating received information. Message recipients tend to perceive information from expert senders as more credible and are thus more likely to be influenced by it.

In line with this, studies have shown that a higher level of sender expertise is directly associated with increased trust and more confident purchasing decisions by recipients (Bansal & Voyer, 2000). This becomes particularly important in situations of uncertainty, where consumers seek guidance. Therefore, the higher an individual's level of expertise, the less dependent they become on others' opinions, and the more independently they make purchasing decisions.

4.9 Message Frequency or Repetition of eWOM

Message frequency refers to the number of times consumers are exposed to information,

5. Methodology

This study is applied in nature, aiming to address a practical issue in the field of marketing—specifically, to examine the impact of electronic service quality and electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) on customers' purchase intentions. The results can assist companies in improving online services and evaluating marketing strategies, while also serving as a reference for students

electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), or reviews. A higher frequency of exposure or a large number of reviews significantly aids consumers in evaluating the quality of a brand or product. The volume of information also indicates how many people are discussing a product, which implies that the product is widely purchased and enjoys a good reputation—ultimately reducing uncertainty during purchase decisions (Ho, 2021). Research by López and Cecilia (2013) and Garmonjonni et al. (2020) revealed that the quantity of information is associated with product popularity, reliability, and effectiveness. A high number of eWOM messages plays a crucial role in enhancing their visibility, credibility, and impact. Consumers often interpret the abundance of reviews as a sign of the product's popularity and successful performance, which positively influences their purchase intention (Ismagilova, 2019). A large volume of reviews creates a sense of assurance and reduces consumer anxiety in decision-making, as it implies that many others have purchased and recommended the product (Rahimian Mohaqeq, 2020). Moreover, high message frequency helps form consistency in user perceptions and suggestions, which strengthens the perceived credibility of the messages (Ismagilova, 2017). Specifically, an increase in the number of reviews makes them more visible (Cheung, 2010) and significantly influences purchase decisions (Godes, 2004). Evidence also suggests that a high quantity of eWOM messages can enhance their perceived credibility and play a key role in reducing the perceived risk for consumers (Sher, 2009).

and researchers in studies related to purchase intention. The statistical population includes all consumers who search for electronic products online and are influenced by eWOM in making their purchase decisions. The sampling method was convenience sampling, and based on the Morgan table, a sample size of 363 respondents was determined. Over a two-week period, a questionnaire was distributed among these individuals, and all 363 completed responses

were collected. The data collection method was field-based, meaning the researcher directly interacted with participants and the phenomena under investigation. A literature review was conducted using library sources, and the primary data were collected via a structured questionnaire.

The measurement scale for the study variables was a 7-point Likert scale, ranging from “Strongly Disagree” (score 1) to “Strongly Agree” (score 7). This methodological structure supports the quantitative analysis of the effects of the selected variables on consumer purchase intention. To ensure validity, face validity was employed. The initial version of the

questionnaire was reviewed by academic supervisors, consultants, and subject matter experts. Based on their feedback, necessary revisions were made to ensure that the questions aligned appropriately with the research objectives.

Reliability, referring to the consistency and stability of the measurement tool, was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha coefficient. This coefficient measures the internal consistency among items, and a value above 0.70 is generally considered acceptable, indicating satisfactory reliability. The next section of the research presents a table showing the Cronbach’s alpha values and item consistency results.

Internal Consistency of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
Excellent	$\alpha \geq 0.9$
Good	$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$
Acceptable	$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$
Questionable	$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$
Poor	$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$
Unacceptable	$\alpha < 0.5$

Table 3-3: Cronbach's Alpha Thresholds

Accordingly, SPSS software was used to calculate Cronbach’s alpha, and a pilot test was conducted for this purpose. In the pilot phase, 40 questionnaires were distributed, and 30 completed responses were collected and analyzed. For the main data collection, a

total of 384 questionnaires were distributed in person among buyers and customers in Tehran’s Grand Bazaar and the capital city, and all were successfully collected. A summary of the process is presented in the following table.

Table 3-4. Results of Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability Test

Indicator	Cronbach’s Alpha	Composite Reliability	Critical Threshold	Result
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	0.704	0.835	0.70	Confirmed
Consumer Expertise	0.709	0.837	0.70	Confirmed
Source Expertise	0.770	0.868	0.70	Confirmed
Message Frequency	0.739	0.851	0.70	Confirmed
Purchase Intention	0.762	0.848	0.70	Confirmed

Table 3-4. Results of Cronbach’s Alpha

The output results for both Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability exceeded the threshold of 0.70, confirming the reliability criteria of the research. Therefore, the measurement model of the study

demonstrates acceptable fit. In this research, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using the Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach was employed for data analysis and hypothesis testing. This variance-based method is

designed through an iterative process, aiming to maximize the explained variance of endogenous variables. SEM, as a combination of factor analysis and path analysis (regression), enables the simultaneous examination of relationships between latent variables (unobserved constructs) and observed variables (indicators). Latent variables, which cannot be measured directly, are assessed through

observable indicators—forming a coherent theoretical construct. For the implementation of SEM and evaluation of model fit, the LISREL software—one of the most widely recognized tools for structural equation analysis—was used. This method allowed the researcher to empirically test the theoretical relationships between constructs and gain a deeper understanding of the structure of the study variables.

6. Findings and Data Analysis

In this section, descriptive statistical indicators such as mean, maximum, and minimum values have been used to describe the collected data. The mean represents the

central tendency of the data, such that replacing all original values with the mean would not alter the total sum of the dataset. The maximum and minimum values respectively indicate the highest and lowest recorded values for each variable.

Table 4-4. Mean and Standard Deviation of Model Variables

Factor	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Consumer Expertise	4.21	1.16	1	6.67
Source Expertise	3.76	1.81	1	7
Message Frequency	3.66	1.87	1	7
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	3.69	1.84	1	7
Purchase Intention	3.68	1.80	1	7

These results indicate that participants' perceptions of the research variables are relatively positive and tend toward the higher

end of the scale, particularly in the case of consumer expertise, which shows a higher mean compared to the other variables.

6.1 Normality Test of Research Variables

In this study, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, a well-established statistical method, was used to examine the normality assumption of the research data. The hypotheses for this test are as follows:

- **H₀**: The data are normally distributed.

- **H₁**: The data are not normally distributed.

According to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results, if the significance level (p-value) for all independent and dependent variables is greater than the 5% error threshold, it can be concluded that the data are normally distributed.

Table 4-5. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Normality Test Results for Research Variables

Variable	Test Statistic	Significance Level	Result
Consumer Expertise	0.107	p < 0.001	Not Normal
Source Expertise	0.160	p < 0.001	Not Normal
Message Frequency	0.140	p < 0.001	Not Normal
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	0.126	p < 0.001	Not Normal
Purchase Intention	0.133	p < 0.001	Not Normal

Based on the values presented in the table above, the significance levels for all variables are less than 0.05, indicating that

the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected. Therefore, the distribution of the variables does not follow a normal distribution. As a

result, non-parametric methods are used to examine the relationships between the research variables and to test the hypotheses

6.2 Correlation Analysis between Research Indicators

Given the non-normal distribution of the data, the Spearman correlation test was employed to assess the relationships between the main variables of the study. The

hypotheses for the correlation analysis are as follows:

- **H₀**: There is no significant relationship between the two variables.
- **H₁**: There is a significant relationship between the two variables.

Table 4-6. Spearman Correlation Coefficients Between Research Variables

Variable	Consumer Expertise	Source Expertise	Message Frequency	Perceived Credibility of eWOM	Purchase Intention
Consumer Expertise	1	-0.108	-0.318	-0.238	-0.210
Source Expertise	-0.108	1	0.504	0.558	0.515
Message Frequency	-0.318	0.504	1	0.494	0.501
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	-0.238	0.558	0.494	1	0.523
Purchase Intention	-0.210	0.515	0.501	0.523	1

The results of the Spearman correlation analysis between the main research variables are presented in the table above. As observed, all correlation coefficients fall within the range of 0 to 1, and the significance levels are less than 0.05 for all relationships. Therefore, the null hypothesis

(H₀) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H₁) is accepted, indicating that there are significant correlations among all the research variables. Consequently, it is appropriate to proceed with hypothesis testing using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

6.3 Measurement Model

To evaluate the measurement model, three key criteria were employed: reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. In the Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach, both Cronbach's alpha and

composite reliability coefficients are used to assess internal consistency. If the values of both composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha for each construct exceed 0.70, it indicates adequate internal reliability for the measurement model. Conversely, values below 0.70 suggest a lack of reliability.

Table 4-7. Results of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability Test

Indicator	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Threshold	Result
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	0.704	0.835	0.70	Confirmed
Consumer Expertise	0.709	0.837	0.70	Confirmed
Source Expertise	0.770	0.868	0.70	Confirmed
Message Frequency	0.739	0.851	0.70	Confirmed
Purchase Intention	0.762	0.848	0.70	Confirmed

The software output shows that both Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values for the study variables are greater than

0.70, confirming the reliability criteria. Therefore, the measurement model demonstrates a good level of fit.

6.4 Convergent Validity of the Study

Factor loadings are calculated by measuring the correlation between the indicators of a construct and the construct itself. According to Hulland (1999), if the factor loading is equal to or greater than 0.40, it indicates that the variance shared between a construct and

its indicators exceeds the variance due to measurement error, and thus the convergent validity of the measurement model is acceptable. It is important to note that if, after calculating the factor loadings, the researcher encounters items (i.e., questionnaire statements) with loadings less than 0.40, those indicators should be revised or eliminated from the model.

Table 4-8. Assessment of Factor Loadings for Indicators

Construct	Item	Factor Loading	Threshold	Result
Consumer Expertise	Question 1	0.817	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 2	0.795	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 3	0.772	0.40	Confirmed
Source Expertise	Question 4	0.888	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 5	0.819	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 6	0.775	0.40	Confirmed
Message Frequency	Question 7	0.815	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 8	0.826	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 9	0.789	0.40	Confirmed
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	Question 10	0.790	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 11	0.749	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 12	0.835	0.40	Confirmed
Purchase Intention	Question 13	0.787	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 14	0.720	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 15	0.766	0.40	Confirmed
	Question 16	0.780	0.40	Confirmed

As shown in the table below, the values of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for all constructs are above the 0.50 threshold.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the model exhibits an acceptable level of convergent validity.

Table 4-9. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Test Results

Construct	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Threshold	Result
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	0.628	0.50	Confirmed
Consumer Expertise	0.632	0.50	Confirmed
Source Expertise	0.687	0.50	Confirmed
Message Frequency	0.657	0.50	Confirmed
Purchase Intention	0.583	0.50	Confirmed

Since the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values fall within an acceptable

range, this confirms the convergent validity of the model.

6.5 Discriminant Validity of the Study

Acceptable discriminant validity in a model indicates that each construct shares more variance with its own indicators than with

other constructs in the model. Discriminant validity is considered satisfactory when the AVE of each construct is greater than the squared correlations between that construct and any other construct in the model.

Table 4-10. Discriminant Validity Assessment Using the Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Construct	Perceived Credibility	Consumer Expertise	Source Expertise	Message Frequency	Purchase Intention
Perceived Credibility	0.792				
Consumer Expertise	-0.533	0.795			
Source Expertise	0.611	-0.563	0.829		
Message Frequency	0.526	-0.593	0.578	0.810	
Purchase Intention	0.564	-0.509	0.596	0.546	0.764

As observed in the matrix above, the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each first-order construct is greater than the correlations between that construct and the others. This confirms acceptable discriminant validity and indicates a good fit for the measurement models of the study. Additionally, the results

suggest that each construct interacts more strongly with its own indicators than with those of other constructs. Ultimately, based on the results obtained, the reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity of the study are confirmed, indicating that the measurement model demonstrates a satisfactory level of fit.

6.6 Structural Model of the Study

Unlike the measurement model, the structural model does not focus on observed variables (items or indicators), but instead examines the latent constructs and the relationships among them. To evaluate the fit of the structural model, the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the endogenous latent

variables is used. A higher R^2 value indicates a better model fit. According to Chin (1998), R^2 values of 0.19, 0.33, and 0.67 are considered to reflect weak, moderate, and strong explanatory power, respectively (Davari & Rezazadeh, 2014, p. 92).

Table 4-11. R^2 (Coefficient of Determination) Results for Endogenous Variables

Endogenous Variable	R^2 Value	Result
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	0.443	Confirmed
Purchase Intention	0.318	Confirmed

Based on the results presented in the table above, the R^2 values for the endogenous constructs are within an acceptable range. Therefore, the structural model of the study demonstrates satisfactory model fit. The Stone-Geisser Q^2 criterion is used to evaluate the predictive relevance of the model. According to Henseler et al. (2009), Q^2

values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 represent small, medium, and large predictive relevance, respectively, for the related construct (Davari & Rezazadeh, 2014). The table below presents the results for the Q^2 criterion.

Table 4-12. Q^2 Criterion Results (Stone-Geisser Predictive Relevance)

Variable	Q^2 Value	Predictive Power
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	0.273	Medium
Consumer Expertise	0.277	Medium
Source Expertise	0.365	Strong
Message Frequency	0.316	Medium
Purchase Intention	0.315	Medium

Since the Q² values for all constructs in the research model are greater than 0.25, this indicates that the model has medium to strong predictive power, thereby confirming the satisfactory fit of the structural model.

$$Gof = \sqrt{R^2 * \text{communitaly}}$$

In this formula, Communality refers to the shared variance derived from the average of the squared factor loadings for each variable. The GOF is calculated as the geometric mean of the average extracted variance (AVE) and the average adjusted R². The value ranges from 0 to 1, where values closer to 1 indicate a better model fit. According to several researchers, a GOF value above 0.36 indicates good model fit, while values between 0.19 and 0.36 suggest moderate fit. In this study, based on the formula and the values from the model, the GOF value was calculated to be 0.491, which confirms that the overall model fit is satisfactory.

6.7 Goodness of Fit Evaluation

The overall model includes both the measurement model and the structural model. By confirming the fit of both components, the overall model fit can be evaluated. The Goodness of Fit (GOF) index pertains to the comprehensive assessment of structural equation models. This index enables the researcher to assess the overall model fit after separately confirming the measurement and structural model components. The GOF value is calculated using the following formula:

Table 4-13. Communality and Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Construct	R ² (Coefficient of Determination)	Communality
Perceived Credibility of eWOM	0.443	0.628
Consumer Expertise	–	0.632
Source Expertise	–	0.687
Message Frequency	–	0.657
Purchase Intention	0.318	0.583

The term model fit refers to the extent to which a proposed model is consistent with and supported by the empirical data. Therefore, in this section, the fit of the hypothesized research model is evaluated to

ensure its alignment with the collected data. Ultimately, this evaluation serves as the basis for drawing conclusions and answering the research questions.

Figure 4-1. Standardized Regression Coefficients of the Research Model

Based on the fitted research model, the standardized regression coefficient of perceived credibility of eWOM on purchase intention is 0.564. The standardized regression coefficient of consumer expertise

on perceived credibility of eWOM is -0.208, that of source expertise on perceived credibility of eWOM is 0.393, and the coefficient of message frequency on perceived credibility of eWOM is 0.175.

Figure 4-2. T-Values of the Research Model

In SmartPLS software, T-values are used to assess the statistical significance of path coefficients. At a 5% significance level, the critical T-value is 1.96. To evaluate significance, each path's T-value is compared to this threshold. If the T-value

exceeds 1.96, the corresponding relationship is considered statistically significant. A summary of the overall model fit and the significance of relationships is presented in the table below.

Table 4-14. Model Fit and Path Significance Results

Path	Standardized Coefficient	T-Statistic	Significance Level
Perceived Credibility of eWOM → Purchase Intention	0.564	15.095	p < 0.001
Consumer Expertise → Perceived Credibility of eWOM	-0.208	3.664	p < 0.001
Source Expertise → Perceived Credibility of eWOM	0.393	6.788	p < 0.001
Message Frequency → Perceived Credibility of eWOM	0.175	2.925	p = 0.004

7. Analysis of Results

7.1 Consumer Expertise Influences Purchase Intention Through the Mediating Role of Perceived eWOM Credibility

According to Figures 4-1 and 4-2, the standardized regression coefficient of consumer expertise on perceived electronic

word-of-mouth (eWOM) credibility is -0.208, and the coefficient of perceived eWOM credibility on purchase intention is 0.564. Additionally, the T-values for these coefficients are greater than 1.96, indicating that the effects are statistically significant at the 5% level. To examine the mediating role of perceived eWOM credibility in the

relationship between consumer expertise and purchase intention, the Sobel test (1982) was applied. Since the T-value obtained from the Sobel test exceeds 1.96, it confirms that

perceived eWOM credibility acts as a significant mediator in the relationship between consumer expertise and purchase intention.

Table 4-15. Sobel Test Results (1982)
Indirect Effect of Consumer Expertise on Purchase Intention

Path	Coefficient	T-Value	Significance Level
Purchase Intention ← Perceived eWOM Credibility ← Consumer Expertise	-0.117	-3.548	P < 0.001

7.2 Source Expertise Influences Consumers' Purchase Intention Through Perceived Electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM) Credibility

According to Figures 4-1 and 4-2, the standardized regression coefficient of source expertise on perceived eWOM credibility is 0.393, and the standardized coefficient of perceived eWOM credibility on purchase intention is 0.564. Furthermore, the T-values

for these coefficients exceed the critical value of 1.96, indicating that these relationships are statistically significant at the 5% error level. To evaluate the mediating role of perceived eWOM credibility in the relationship between source expertise and purchase intention, the Sobel test was employed. The results showed that the Sobel test statistic (1982) exceeds the threshold of 1.96, confirming that perceived eWOM credibility acts as a mediator between source expertise and consumers' purchase intention.

Table 4-16. Sobel Test Results (1982)
Indirect Effect of Source Expertise on Purchase Intention

Pathway	Coefficient	T-Value	Significance Level
Purchase Intention ← Perceived eWOM Credibility ← Source Expertise	0.221	6.191	P < 0.001

7.3 Message Frequency has an indirect effect on Purchase Intention through Perceived eWOM Credibility.

According to Figures 4-1 and 4-2, the standardized regression coefficient of Message Frequency on Perceived eWOM Credibility is 0.175, and the coefficient of Perceived eWOM Credibility on Purchase Intention is 0.564. Additionally, the T-values for these coefficients exceed the critical

value of 1.96, indicating statistical significance at the 5% error level. To assess the mediating role of Perceived eWOM Credibility in the relationship between Message Frequency and Purchase Intention, Sobel's test (1982) was conducted. The result shows that the T-value of the Sobel test exceeds 1.96, confirming that Perceived eWOM Credibility mediates the effect of Message Frequency on Purchase Intention

Table 4-17. Results of Sobel Test (1982)
Indirect Effect of Source Expertise on Message Frequency

Pathway	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Significance Level
Purchase Intention ← Perceived eWOM Credibility ← Message Frequency	0.098	2.864	0.002

7.4 The perceived credibility of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) significantly influences consumers' purchase intention.

According to Figures 4-1 and 4-2, the standardized regression coefficient of perceived eWOM credibility on purchase intention is 0.564. Additionally, the t-statistic for this coefficient is 15.095, which exceeds the critical value of 1.96, indicating statistical significance at the 5% error level.

Overall, the results obtained from the model estimation suggest that the perceived credibility of electronic word-of-mouth has a significant effect on consumers' purchase intention.

8. Practical Recommendations:

Based on the findings of the study, electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) plays a significant role in influencing consumers' purchase intentions. Accordingly, companies should enhance the quality of their products and services to foster the generation of positive eWOM. Utilizing the internet and social media in the design of advertising strategies can provide a substantial competitive advantage.

Proper training of organizational staff is

essential, as they contribute directly or indirectly to the formation of word-of-mouth communication. Furthermore, investing in branding and customer experience can create a positive image in the consumer's mind and increase the likelihood of sharing positive experiences.

9. Suggestions for Future Research:

Future studies may provide a more comprehensive analysis by incorporating individual and psychological variables that influence consumers' perceptions and responses to electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM). These may include:

- Examining the role of age, gender, education level, level of cognitive involvement, and quality of reasoning in the eWOM influence process.
- Analyzing cultural or behavioral differences among various customer groups in response to eWOM messages.
- Expanding the research model to investigate purchase behavior across more diverse industries such as apparel, tourism, financial services, and food services.

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Appendices

Questionnaire

Item	Strongly Agree	Very Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Very Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. I have sufficient knowledge about the desired product.							
2. I am able to distinguish good-quality products from fake or low-quality ones.							
3. I have different ideas compared to others.							
4. Reviewers on websites have experienced the product quality and are capable of evaluating products.							
5. People who share their opinions on websites are trustworthy and experienced.							
6. Reviewers on websites are well-informed, and their opinions give me confidence.							
7. The fact that many people recommend the product shows that it has a good reputation.							
8. Reviews about the product reduce my anxiety when purchasing.							
9. A large number of reviews about the product indicates that it is popular in society.							
10. People who share their reviews about my desired products can persuade me.							
11. Individuals who post reviews on websites are highly knowledgeable.							
12. When purchasing a product online, reviews on websites reassure me that I made a good purchase.							
13. After reading user reviews online, I enjoy purchasing products.							
14. After reading user reviews online, I try to buy new products.							
15. When shopping, based on reviews and research I've done online, my desired product becomes my first priority.							
16. My desired product is a purchase priority, and I prefer to gather information before buying it.							

Table 3-2. Variables and Sources of Questionnaire Design

Variable	Item	Question	Dimension	Source
Consumer Expertise	1	I have sufficient knowledge about the intended product.	7-point Likert scale	
	2	I can distinguish good products from fake or low-quality ones.		
	3	I have different ideas compared to others.		
Source Expertise	4	Reviewers on websites have experienced the product and can evaluate them.	7-point Likert scale	Imanina (2016)
	5	People who share their opinions on websites are trustworthy and experienced.		
	6	Reviewers are knowledgeable, and their opinions give me confidence.		
Message Frequency (Quantity)	7	Since many people recommend the product, it shows the product has a good reputation.	7-point Likert scale	Imanina (2016)
	8	Reviews about the product reduce my purchase anxiety.		
	9	The high number of reviews indicates the product is popular in society.		
Perceived Credibility of (eWOM)	10	Those who express their opinions on websites can convince me.	7-point Likert scale	
	11	Those individuals have high knowledge and can influence others.		
	12	When purchasing a product online, reviews on websites reassure me about the purchase.		
Purchase Intention	13	After reading reviews online, I enjoy purchasing products.	7-point Likert scale	
	14	After reading online reviews, I try to buy new products.		
	15	When buying, the product I researched online is my top priority.		
	16	The desired product is among my purchase priorities, and I prefer to gather information beforehand.		